

Studies on the Addition of Hydrogen Halides to Butadiene.

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If it is held that the butadienoid unit may polarise in two ways

leading to reaction at adjacent C atoms of the chain, it can be expected

that the addition of a substance of the nature $\overset{+}{A} - \overset{-}{B}$ to butadiene should yield 3 isomerides of the types (1) $CH_2A - CHB - CH = CH_2$, (2) $CH_2A - CH = CH - CH_2B$ and (3) $CH_2B - CHA - CH = CH_2$ depending upon whether the addition takes place at 1:2, 1:4 or 3:4 carbon atoms of the chain.

Addition of bromine to butadiene was studied by Grinner (*Compt. rend.*, 1863, 116, 723; 1864, 117, 553) and of chlorine by Muskat and Northup (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 52, 4043). In both these cases, the authors obtained both 1:2- and 1:4- isomerides, only two being theoretically possible.

Addition of ICl to the hydrocarbon was examined by Ingold and Smith (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 2754) and they could trace the presence of only two isomerides namely (1) $CH_2I - CHCl - CH = CH_2$ and (2) $CH_2I - CH = CH - CH_2Cl$, whereas the third theoretically possible isomeride, (3) $CH_2Cl - CHI - CH = CH_2$ was never obtained.

Since the entrance of the iodine atom is regarded as marking the point of incidence of the reaction, this experiment favours the view that the point of incidence of the reaction in the butadienoid chain is C_1 and not the C_2 atom.

In the addition of hydrogen halides, however, the point of incidence of the reaction, as deduced from the polarity of the substituents, is marked by the point of entrance of hydrogen. The stable position of the halogen then depends on anionotropic equilibrium as affected by the substituents present, including that which has become modified by the accession of the hydrogen atom. The first of these conclusions is confirmed, without complications related to the second, by the formation of compounds having the properties of allyl halide, from cyclopentadiene and cyclohexadiene.

The hydrogen of the hydrogen halide attaches to the C₁ atom (Kraemar and Spilker, *Ber.*, 1896, 29, 554; Crossly, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1904, 85, 1420).

In support of the second view, already mentioned, reference may be made to Farmer and Marshall's demonstration that the monohydrobromide of dimethylbutadiene [CH₂:C(Me)·C(Me):CH₂] prepared under a variety of conditions, in all cases consist essentially of the product [H·CH₂C(Me)·C(Me)·CH₂Br] (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 139).

In the light of these results it can be expected that the addition of HBr or HCl to butadiene should yield only two isomerides, namely (1) CH₃·CHX·CH:CH₂ and (2) CH₃·CH:CH·CH₂X; the possibility of the formation of the third one, CH₂X·CH₂·CH:CH₂ being thus ruled out on theoretical grounds.

Addition of hydrogen chloride to the hydrocarbon resulted in the formation of two addition products which were identified as Δ^{3:4}-2 chlorobutene and Δ^{2:3}-4 chlorobutene.

To effect a direct comparison of these addition products with authentic specimens, the two chlorobutenes were prepared from methylvinylcarbinol by treatment with four or five times its weight of concentrated hydrochloric acid.

An attempt has been made to prepare the hitherto-undescribed isomeric chlorobutene (CH₂Cl·CH₂·CH:CH₂) from allyl carbinol, prepared by the action of *para*-formaldehyde on allyl bromide in presence of magnesium (Pariselle, *Ann chim.*, 1928, 9, 412). On treatment with concentrated hydrochloric acid, the compound obtained was mostly a di-addition product instead of the desired chlorobutene.

Since no definite conclusion could be reached as to the absence of the third isomeride, namely CH₂Cl·CH₂·CH:CH₂, no attempt was made to determine quantitatively the proportion of the Δ^{3:4}-2- and Δ^{2:3}-4- chlorobutenes in the reaction product. Such a determination of the percentage composition of the mixture was proposed to be accomplished from the refractive index composition curve, which according to expectations was found to be a straight line.

Addition of hydrogen bromide resulted in the formation of only one compound, b.p. 104-107° identified to be CH₃·CH:CH·CH₂Br by comparing its properties with an authentic specimen of the same, prepared synthetically from methylvinyl carbinol.

Transformation of the crude addition product to the acetoxy derivative was also tried. On purification and final distillation, a product

boiling at $130-35^{\circ}$ was collected. This was identified to be $\text{CH}_3\text{CH}:\text{CH}\cdot\text{CH}\cdot\text{O}\cdot\text{COCH}_3$ by direct comparison with an authentic specimen of the same.

On an attempt to study the action of hydrogen bromide on methyl-vinyl carbinol Baudrenghem (*Bull. Soc. chim. Belg.*, 1922, 31, 160) obtained only one substance namely $\Delta^{2:3}$ -4-bromobutene, whereas the isomeride $\Delta^{3:4}$ -2-bromobutene which was more likely to be formed by the reaction, could not be isolated from the reaction product. This suggests, however, that $\Delta^{3:4}$ -2-bromobutene, which might have been formed at the start, subsequently underwent anionotropic change in a similar manner as observed by Farmer and Marshall in the preparation of monohydrobromide of dimethylbutadiene to the more stable variety.

The above argument regarding the anionotropic change of the $\Delta^{3:4}$ -2- to $\Delta^{2:3}$ -4-bromobutene, gains more support in view of the fact that while both the corresponding acetoxy derivatives are known to be perfectly stable compounds, bromobutene has not yet been successfully isolated by any method.

The difference between the behaviour of hydrogen chloride and hydrogen bromide on butadiene is probably due to the difference in their (i) dipole moment and thereby the permanent inductive electronic drift and more so (ii) the molecular volume—it being an established fact that there is a connection between the bulk of the new entrant and its orienting power (*cf. Le Fevre, J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 980; also Ganguly and Le Fevre, *ibid.*, 1934, 848, 852, 1697).

Furthermore, such an explanation is in perfect agreement to the observation of Gillet (*cf. Farmer, Lawrence and Thorpe, J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 729), who concludes that hydrogen bromide suggests itself as a probable accelerator of 1:2 $\rightarrow$ 1:4 change.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Butadiene (*cf. Farmer, Lawrence and Thorpe, loc. cit.*). The gas obtained by heating "railway hydrocarbon" was passed through wash-bottles containing bromine and immersed in ice, till the latter was completely consumed. Butadiene tetrabromide, thus prepared along with other impurities was washed with ligroin and recrystallised from the same solvent till it melted at 117° .

Reduction of the Tetrabromide.—The tetrabromide thus prepared was reduced to butadiene by the method described by Thiele.

Before being collected in tubes immersed in a freezing mixture of solid carbon dioxide and ether, the gas was further purified by passing through (i) a spiral immersed in ice and salt; (ii) a calcium chloride tube immersed in a freezing mixture of ice and salt, and finally (iii) through phosphorus pentoxide to effect complete drying. Butadiene was collected in sealed tubes and kept in a refrigerator till further use.

The hydrogen chloride and hydrogen bromide used have been purified by passing through (i) moist red phosphorus, (ii) U-tubes containing calcium chloride and immersed in a mixture of solid carbon dioxide and ether and finally through, (iii) phosphorous pentoxide. The gases were then collected in Carius tubes immersed in liquid air.

Methylvinyl Carbinol.—Methyl bromide (100 g.) mixed with four or five times its volume of dry ether was added drop by drop in about an hour and a half to magnesium (24 g.), suspended in dry ether (1000 c.c.) in a three-necked round bottomed flask fitted with a reflux condenser and a mechanical stirrer. Stirring was continued during the whole operation and the temperature was kept below 15°. It was then allowed to stand for another couple of hours. Acrolein (67 g.), mixed with four or five times its volume of dry ether, was then added (with stirring) to the mixture during 2 hours. The process being complete, the flask was heated up to 15° and allowed to stand for 18 hours. The reaction product was then hydrolysed by means of a saturated solution of ammonium chloride (1000 c.c.) and just sufficient amount of hydrochloric acid. The ethereal layer was separated, dried over potassium carbonate and then barium oxide for 3 or 4 days, ether removed and the product collected at 96-97°, yield 20 g.

Addition of Hydrogen Bromide to Butadiene.—Anhydrous hydrogen bromide was added to butadiene in the proportion of 1:1; addition took place easily. The crude product obtained was washed with water and dried over potassium carbonate. The greater portion distilled at 101°-107° and some above 150°, with decomposition. The fraction below 101° was redistilled, but no indication of its containing a substance boiling at a definite temperature lower than 104° was obtained. The portion boiling at 101-107° was redistilled and collected at 104-107°; n_D^{20} , 1.4797; d^{21} , 1.3342.

Treatment of Methylvinyl Carbinol with Hydrobromic Acid.—Methylvinyl carbinol (20 g.) was mixed with hydrobromic acid (d 1.7,

50 g.) and left in a mechanical shaker for 4—5 hours. At the end of the process, the product was neutralised with potassium carbonate, washed with water and the oily layer dried over potassium carbonate and distilled at 101°-107°. It was redistilled at 101°-104°; d^{19} 1.339; n_D^{20} , 1.47816.

Acetoxy Derivative of $\Delta^{2:3}$ -4-Bromobutene.—The bromobutene was treated with fused potassium acetate, acetic acid and a trace of potassium iodide. The oily layer was dried over calcium chloride and distilled at 132°-35°; d^{21} , 0.8539; n_D^{20} , 1.43256.

Addition of Hydrogen Chloride to Butadiene.—The reaction was not complete even in 10 days. The crude addition product was washed with water, dried over calcium chloride and fractionated into 2 parts, (i) one distilling at 62°-74° and (ii) the other at 74°-84°. By repeating the distillation of (i) a substance distilling at 64-68° and (ii) the other at 80°, were obtained.

According to Baudrengheim (*loc. cit.*) 1:2-chlorobutene ($\text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2\text{ClCH:CH}_2$) boils at 64-65°, whereas the corresponding 1:4-product boils at 84-85°/766 mm.

Treatment of Methylvinyl Carbinol with Hydrochloric Acid.—Methyl vinyl carbinol (20 g.) was mixed in a strong bottle with hydrochloric acid (d 1.16. 60 c. c.). The mixture was then left in a mechanical shaker (3 to 4 hours). The reaction mixture was then washed with water and extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was washed with sodium carbonate and again with water and the ether removed and dried over calcium chloride and distilled at 60°-87°. On redistillation two fractions were obtained *viz.*, (i) 1:2-chlorobutene, 64°-68°/757 mm. and (ii) 1:4-chlorobutene, 80°/757 mm.

Refractive Index of 1:2-and 1:4-Chlorobutenes at 21 .

All observations on the determinations of refractive indices were done with a Pulfrich refractometer with reference to sodium D line.

Chlorobutenes		Angle of refraction.
1:2—	1:4—	
0 %	100 %	50° 10
21	79	52° 44
51.7	48.3	53° 59
100	0	55° 44

Acetoxy Derivative of the Addition product of Hydrogen Bromide to Butadiene.—The crude addition product was mixed with fused potassium iodide (*cf. Bull. Soc. chim. Belg.*, 1922, 31, 160), when the mixture became almost solid, with evolution of heat. On heating it on the water-bath, the solid diminished and liquid increased. The mass was poured into water, and the acetic acid was neutralised with sodium carbonate. The oily layer was separated, dried over calcium chloride, and distilled at 130°-136°. The fraction below 130° gave the substance boiling at 130°-36° on repeated distillation, and there was no indication of its containing a definite substance with lower boiling point, and although it contained some unchanged bromo compound, no trace of $\text{CH}_3\text{CH}(\text{OCOCH}_3)\text{CH}:\text{CH}_2$, could be isolated, d^{20} , 0.8541; n_D^{20} , 1.4.

SUMMARY.

1. Addition of hydrogen bromide to butadiene leads to the production of $\Delta^{2:3}$ -4-bromobutene only.
2. Addition of hydrogen chloride to butadiene leads to the formation of two isomerides (a) $\Delta^{2:3}$ -4-chlorobutene and (b) $\Delta^{3:4}$ -2-chlorobutene.
3. The properties of these addition products are compared with authentic specimens of the same prepared synthetically.
4. An explanation has been advanced to interpret the results obtained in the light of the modern concepts of the electronic theory of valency.

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